

DURABILITY OF POLYIMIDE COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO THERMOMECHANICAL FATIGUE IN REUSABLE PROPULSION SYSTEMS

John C. Thesken¹, E. Eugene Shin¹, James K. Sutter², Chris Burke³, and Jeff Fink⁴
¹ OAI, ² NASA-GRC and ³ QSS at
NASA Glenn Research Center, 21000 Brookpark Rd., Cleveland, OH 44135
¹ Tel: 216-433-3012, Fax: 216-433-5649, E-mail: John.C.Thesken@grc.nasa.gov
⁴ Boeing-Rocketdyne, Canoga Park, CA 91309-7922

Summary: Reusable propulsion systems for manned space flight face stringent durability and safety requirements. As Boeing and NASA-GRC seek to introduce polyimide composites to the harsh environmental and loads familiar to space launch, serious consideration is being given to the synergistic effects of temperature and mechanical loads. The candidate component operates at 316 °C, about 80% of the polyimide's glass transition temperature (T_g). Earlier thermomechanical fatigue (TMF) investigations of chopped fiber polyimide composites made this near to T_g , showed that cyclic temperature and stress promoted excessive creep damage and strain accumulation. In current propulsion applications where stiffness and deformation tolerances are operations critical, it is important to verify that such response is limited in continuous fiber cross-ply laminates.

The study will compare the isothermal and thermomechanical fatigue of stitched and unstitched cross-ply laminates of M40J carbon fiber reinforced polyimide. Isothermal test temperature and the maximum cyclic temperature of TMF tests were chosen as the maximum operation temperature, 316 °C. The mechanical load cycle is identical in both isothermal and thermomechanical testing. The load magnitudes were guided by the results of stress analysis of the actual component. Test waveforms for thermal and mechanical load cycles are in-phase and were chosen to be representative of an engine operation cycle.

Deformation and stiffness degradation due to fatigue loading is monitored periodically during each fatigue test. Residual strength testing and microscopic observations are being made to quantify the extent of the damage. Isothermal and thermomechanical fatigue performance is compared to deduce the presence of synergistic effects. Also the influence of stitching on the long term durability of the material is studied. Thus far only stitched materials have been tested and their fatigue response is reported here providing guidelines for design of durable structures.

KEY WORDS: Durability, Thermomechanical Fatigue, Polyimide Composites, Reusable Propulsion Systems

INTRODUCTION

Polyimide composites are being used in lightweight support structures designed to preserve the ideal flow geometry within thin shell combustion chambers of reusable launch propulsion systems. While the continuous carbon fiber enables a cross-ply laminated skin of high specific stiffness; the polyimide matrix materials ensure that the rigidity and durability is maintained at operation temperatures of 316 C or 80% of the polyimide's T_g . Design analysis of prototype composite supports have shown that the chamber's stiffness requirements are met initially met while achieving significant weight savings over existing metallic supports [1]. The challenge is to ensure that the stiffness and strength of the composite support is maintained over its expected design life. Indeed, available creep data for similar woven polyimide composites [2]

suggest that deflections could increase by about 10% in one hour at temperatures near the T_g . It is expected that thermomechanical cycling might accelerate such deformation.

This effort is part of the ongoing HOTPC collaboration between Boeing Rocketdyne and NASA-GRC seeking to introduce polyimide composites to the harsh environmental and loads familiar to space launch propulsion systems[3,4,5]. While life requirements may only be of the order 200 cycles, stringent durability and safety requirements for reusable launch systems require that the synergistic effects of cyclic temperature and mechanical loads in polymer matrix composites (PMCs) be understood. Consequently there is a need to develop and apply experimental methods to determine the thermomechanical fatigue (TMF) response of polyimide composites.

TMF studies of PMCs are not widely available in the open literature. The most relevant existing work by Castelli and co-workers [6] looks at the TMF response of chopped fiber reinforced PMR-15, a polyimide composite in the form of sheet molding compounds (SMCs). Tests made at temperatures up to 80% of T_g , showed that cyclic temperature and stress promoted excessive creep damage and strain accumulation [6]. After 120 mission cycles, strain off-sets of the order 0.05% to 0.1% were measured at zero load. From a design standpoint, this corresponds to an increase in deflection at operating load of about 8 to 16%. In propulsion applications where stiffness and deformation tolerances are operations critical, it is important to verify that such response in cross-ply polyimide laminates is within design limits.

Thus far the physical and mechanical properties of polyimide composites have been studied over a range of hygrothermal states[2-5,7,8]. These studies have included investigations of degradation due to steam induced blistering in high temperature PMCs and point to the usefulness of laminate stitching as a preventive measure[2,7,8]. In particular, rates of transverse expansion as a function of temperature is reduced in moisture conditioned stitched specimens and is comparable to unstitched vacuum dried laminates.[8] However, the improved blistering resistance by stitching is offset by a reduction of in-plane properties; the dry ultimate tensile strength of the stitched laminate at elevated temperature was reduced by 40% with respect to unstitched laminate. While the other laminate variables were not strictly controlled in this comparison, the underlying trend is consistent with other studies on the influence of stitching[3,9]. The reduction of in-plane strength is likely due to misalignment, distortion and damage of the primary reinforcing fibers accompanied by resin rich regions, porosity and resin cracking. The existence of such stitching induced defects would likely be sources for non-recoverable strains in TMF. Since stitching has been shown to reduce the in-plane mechanical performance of composite laminates[3,8,9], an evaluation of the influence of stitching on TMF response is an important element of this investigation.

The objective of this work is to determine the isothermal fatigue and TMF response of stitched and unstitched cross-ply laminates of M40J carbon fiber in an HFPE polyimide matrix. The stitched laminate was manufactured by Boeing, Huntington Beach using proprietary stitching and resin infusion methods. The exploratory test plan aims to quickly establish performance limitations and provide design guidelines for the intended application of the composite. While the TMF cycle was synthesized from Boeing Rocketdynes operation data, an effort was made to use a sufficiently generic test cycle to be of scientific value. However, the nature of the applied TMF cycle and the test material combined to present some challenges in test method development. These difficulties are reviewed and discussed along with directions for future work. Thus far only tests on stitched laminates have been completed and these results are presented.

While it would seem preferable to have TMF data reflecting the true nature of the operation cycle such efforts might be unnecessary if the isothermal fatigue degradation is identical or more severe than the TMF degradation. Therefore a number of baseline isothermal fatigue tests have been made using identical loading waveforms to determine the relative influence of TMF testing. The maximum loads selected for these tests are guided by analysis of the expected operations stresses in the PMC support using analytical and finite element methods [1]. Due to the duration of a cycle, 480 s, the number of loading cycles did not

exceed about 2000 on any one specimen. This meant that fatigue experiments were rarely of sufficient duration to cause failure. Nevertheless the fatigue data are in a regime having safety factors of 2 or greater relative to the expected operations envelop for the support structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials A detailed description of the matrix materials being evaluated in this NASA-GRC/Boeing Rocketdyne collaboration, including HFPE-II-52 polyimide resin used here, is given in [10]. The M40JB carbon fiber is manufactured by Toray Carbon Fibers America, Inc., Santa Ana, CA having a tensile modulus of 377 GPa, strain to failure of 1.2% and a density of 1.77 g/cm³. Uni-fabrics with 110 gm/m² fiber area weight (FAW) from M fibers were fabricated at Sigmatech High Technology Fabrics, Inc., Benicia, CA. The 24 ply uni-tape panels were fabricated using a 12 ply symmetric cross-ply lay-up as in [3]. Dry performs were stitched, infused and cured by Boeing using proprietary and/or restricted methods. Autoclave curing reaches temperatures of 371 °C and pressures of 1.6 MPa. After manufacturing, ultrasonic scans were made to document laminate quality.

2. Test Methods The static and fatigue test methods were guided by *the Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials (ASTM D3039)* and *the Standard Test Method for Tension-Tension Fatigue of Polymer Matrix Composites (ASTM D3479)* The TMF test methods described here are an extension of those presented in [6].

Fig. 1 PMC dogbone specimen design for static tension and tension/tension fatigue (lengths in mm)

Finished panels were sectioned into coupon specimens using abrasive water jet machining. Stitched specimens were sectioned so that loads are applied parallel to the stitch direction. The coupon specimen is the dog bone geometry shown in Fig. 1 that has been used successfully in several test programs of mat, woven and cross-ply PMCs [2,6,11]. The large curvature of the dog bone enable successful testing without tabbing materials. The width of the specimen in the gauge section is 19.05 mm. Specimens were typically

about 2.92 mm thick with a variability of about ± 0.13 mm. As the stitch rows are spaced about 5 mm to 6 mm, care was taken to ensure that 4 rows of stitching were centered on each specimen. Cut specimens were dried for 48 hrs at 150 °C and 760 mm Hg vacuum and then stored in a desiccator until testing.

Fig. 2 Experimental set-up

Fig. 3 Cooling cage

Mechanical loads were applied to the specimen using a closed-loop, servo-hydraulic load frame manufactured by MTSTM having a load capacity of 89 kN. Specimens were gripped using hydraulic actuated

and SurfAlloy™ wedge grips. Axial strains were measured over a 12.7 mm gauge length by an MTS™ air cooled extensometer. A CVD™ powered bank of quartz lamps was used to heat the specimen during isothermal and TMF testing. Radiant heating by quartz lamps is necessary to meet the dynamic heating requirements of these TMF tests. Edge and side views of the specimen set-up are shown in Fig. 2. Rapid cooling during the TMF cycle is facilitated by impinging compressed air on the specimen through air slits in a copper tubing cooling cage. A photograph of the dismantled cooling cage and a specimen is shown in Fig. 3.

Test control and data acquisition was accomplished using the Test Express™ 4.0 software and hardware McGaw Technology, Inc. . The desired load and temperature control waveforms were synthesized from a prototypical operations cycle and are shown in Fig.4 for a max stress of 276 MPa. Start points for thermal and loading ramps are in-phase and the period for the operations cycle is 480 s. The loading waveform is a tensile square wave having load and unload ramps of 40 s and dwell times of 200 s at max stress and zero stress. During launch and shut down the PMC support structure would reach operating temperature extremes in a few seconds. The most representative thermal cycle would be a square wave form having a T_{max} of 316 °C and a T_{min} of room temperature (RT), each having a dwell time slightly less than 240 s. Details of the actual thermal wave form for these TMF tests will be described further below. Throughout the test program, isothermal fatigue and TMF control cycles were programmed having identical loading wave forms. Based on analysis of the composite supports [1] the maximum operation stress in the prototype composite support is about 138 MPa. Full scale designs might achieve greater maximum applied stresses so the stresses examined here ranged from 138 to 483 MPa and could be changed between specific blocks of fatigue cycles. A typical test block was 500 cycles. The isothermal test temperature and maximum TMF temperature (T_{max}) were programmed to be identical at 316 C. The entire period for a TMF cycle is 480 s.

Fig. 4 Desired TMF Cycle

Fig. 5 Control block and calibration specimen thermocouple temperatures

Temperature measurement and control during testing of PMCs is encumbered by the inability to attach thermocouples (TCs) to each test specimen. Following techniques developed in [12] and applied in several fatigue testing programs [2,8,11], temperatures in the position of the test gage section are measured using a calibration specimen with an array of thermocouples. These are correlated to a control TC in a block of the PMC that is positioned adjacent to the specimen (see Fig. 2 side view). The calibration specimen is prepared by drilling holes at specific locations and inserting K-type TCs into these holes. Similarly a control block of PMC is prepared with its own K-type TC. Axial and transverse temperature variations are then measured in the gage section and correlated to the control TC. Adjustments of the quartz lamps and cooling cage are made to minimize thermal gradients in the specimen gage section. A correlation of the control block TC and the specimen gage length are made for both isothermal and cyclic thermal cases. In the case of isothermal tests the specimen is allowed to reach an equilibrium stage which makes this correlation constant with time. For the isothermal testing this correlation was repeatable to within ± 2 °C.

For the TMF testing performed here, the specimen does not have time to reach an equilibrium state. Since the thermal boundary conditions on the specimen and control block are different an iterative procedure is used to develop a control wave form that will yield the desired temperature field in the specimen gage length. The control block temperature and corresponding specimen temperatures for the best simulation of this operation cycle that was achievable in this set-up are shown in Fig.3. The top, middle and bottom specimen temperatures are from positions at the edges and middle of a 25.4 mm segment of the specimen gauge length. The initial heating rate for the specimen was found to be 12 °C/s for the first 25 s of the cycle. The initial cooling rate is about 6 °C/s for the first 25 s of the cool down part of the cycle. A slight positive increase in the control block temperature must occur during the hold period to maintain the temperature in the middle of the specimen close to 316 °C. The radiant heat flux to the specimen must increase slightly to compensate for non-equilibrium heat loss to the grips. The high power levels needed for rapid heating create a noisy environment for the TC. It is important to note that the variability in the temperature measurement for this TMF cycle is 5 to 10 times greater relative to the isothermal temperature measurements. The scatter band for the TC data is about ± 10 to ± 20 °C. When the lamps are turned off this variability decreases down to ± 2 °C. T_{min} for these tests was about 31 to 33 °C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Static tests Two static tests were made to determine the elastic modulus (E), ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and strain to failure.

Table 1. Static Test Results

E (GPa)	UTS (MPa)	Strain to failure (%)
63.1	588	0.8
72.4	545	0.75

2. Isothermal fatigue A summary of the isothermal tests made at 316 °C is given in Table 2. Unless otherwise mentioned in the discussion, stress values are the maximum values for the fatigue cycle.

Table 2. Isothermal Test Matrix

Specimen	Peak Stress (MPa)	Cycle Count
A	276	1 to 2000
B	138	1 to 500
B	207	501-1000
B	276	1001 -1500
C	414	1-1015
C	483	1015-2015
D	483	1-200

Figure 6 gives the isothermal stress-strain response for cycle 1 and cycle 500 of specimen A fatigued at a peak stress of 276 MPa. The hysteresis loop for cycle 500 is translated to the right indicating an accumulative strain of 0.02 %. This strain ratcheting phenomenon was observed for all of the isothermal tests and the amount of strain accumulation is plotted as a function of fatigue cycle in Fig. 7. Specimen B is initially fatigued at a peak stress of 138 MPa to see if there is a threshold for this behavior above the expected operating stress. It appears in Fig. 7 that the strain accumulation for specimen B is fairly similar to specimen A up to 1000 cycles. At 276 MPa the strain accumulation in specimen B is slightly greater than in specimen A. The remaining 2 specimens were fatigued at stress levels up to 80- 88% of the composites UTS. Specimen C acquired 0.13% strain in 1000 cycles at 414 MPa. The accumulated strain in the specimen increased to 0.25% after 1000 cycles at 483 MPa. Specimen D began at a maximum stress of 483 MPa accumulated over 0.1% strain in 200 cycles. Figure 7 shows that the initial rate of strain accumulation

for maximum stress above 80% UTS is significantly greater than at stresses around 50% UTS or twice the operating stress.

Fig. 6 Stress-strain response at 316 °C

Fig. 7 Accumulated off-set strain as a function of fatigue cycle

Changes in the measured elastic modulus are often regarded as a global measure of the internal damage state of composite materials. Despite the translation of the hysteresis loops to the right with accumulated strain as observed in Fig. 6, there is no remarkable change in the slope of the stress-strain response. The control software was programmed to make periodic regressions on the load and unload ramps to compute elastic modulus and these results are given in Fig. 8 as a function of fatigue cycle. While certain specimen to specimen variations are apparent, the elastic modulus values of any one specimen are not found to significantly degrade during the test. This behavior is consistent with observations reported by Castelli et al [6] for SMC composites.

Fig. 8 Elastic modulus as a function of fatigue cycle

Apparently the primary load bearing fibers are not being significantly degraded by these short duration fatigue tests. It is suspected that the presence of a variety of stitching defects provides sites for permanent relative deformations to take place. For example, broken fibers could slip relative to each other without appreciably changing the global stiffness of the specimen.

3. *TMF Results* The TMF test cases that have been completed and evaluated thus far are summarized in Table 3. It should be mentioned that progress with TMF testing has been impeded by fatigue failures of the quartz lamps after about 500 to 800 cycles. Bulb replacement is time consuming and includes recalibration procedures. Increasing cooling air flow to the

lamps appears to have extended bulb life.

Table 3. TMF Test Matrix

Specimen	Peak Stress (MPa)	Cycle Count
E	276	1 to 1623
F	483	1 to 500
G	483	1 to 500

Each TMF test began with a pair of thermal cycles without load to evaluate the thermal expansion response of the specimen. Figure 9 shows the strain measurement as a function of time for the first block of 450 cycles that are applied to specimen E. The thermal expansion is seen to have a maximum value of about 0.05% strain but this is not constant. The initial thermal cycles without load show the extensometer to be measuring an initial rapid thermal expansion followed by shrinkage once maximum temperature had been reached. On cool down the reverse effect was observed; the extensometer measures a rapid contraction followed by a thermal expansion. The qualitative form of the shrinkage and expansion occurring at the extreme temperatures appears to be of exponential decay as a function of time. Thermal trials with the calibration specimen showed that holding the temperature constant at the peak value allows the strain measurement to eventually reach a constant value.

Fig. 9 TMF strain response as a function of time,specimen E

Fig. 10 TMF stress-strain response of specimen E

The reversal of deformation at temperature extremes is counter intuitive to the expected first order response of the specimen. Indeed the cross head displacements continue to increase during the heating cycle to maintain zero applied load. Reducing the cooling air pressure was found to retard the initial expansion response and the subsequent amount of shrinkage was smaller. Thermocouple measurements at the extensometer heat shield showed that the heat shield experienced a change in temperature of about 7 °C between max and min temperature. Concerned that the extensometer may be experiencing thermal fluctuations, a validation test was made using a stainless steel specimen. Placing a stainless steel specimen into the grips and subjecting it to the same heating cycle produced a strain measurement that was at all time consistent with the sign of the temperature change. The measurement is not being effected by the cyclic variations in temperature so there is confidence that the measurement reflects the local behavior of the specimen in the gauge length.

While investigation continues to determine the cause of this behavior it will not be possible to accurately separate the thermal and mechanical strains in the current data set. Nevertheless certain important observations can be made about the data collected thus far. Figure 10 shows the TMF stress-total strain response for cycle 1 and cycle 450 of specimen E. The hysteresis loops coincide with no strain off-set. The absence of strain accumulation persisted throughout this experiment until the specimen failed at 1623 cycles. There was no forewarning of impending failure from the slope of the stress-total strain curve for this specimen. The “apparent stiffness” of specimen E actually increased over the duration of the test by about 14% from 63 GPa to 71 GPa and this is not perceived as a harbinger of failure.

The failure of specimen E at 1623 cycles prompted an increase in TMF peak stress to 483 MPa or about 88% of the UTS for specimen F and specimen G. Figure 11 and 12 shows the stress-total strain response for cycle 1 and cycle 500. Here a significant amount of strain off-set is observed in both curves: 0.38% for

specimen F and 0.16% for specimen G. For these tests, changes in the apparent stiffness of the specimen were of the order $\pm 3\%$. The TMF and isothermal elastic modulus and accumulated strain results for specimens tested at 483 MPa have been summarized in Fig. 13. It should be noted that the elastic modulus values for the TMF tests are based on the stress-total strain slope which includes the influence of thermal expansion. The values from the TMF test Fig. 13(a) are within the range of specimen to specimen variation seen in Fig. 8. This is reasonable since thermal strain is a smaller percentage of the total strain at higher loads. If the maximum of thermal strain is about 0.05% strain for a given TMF cycle then the influence on total strain at 483 MPa is less than 10%.

Fig. 11 TMF stress-strain response of specimen F

Fig. 12 TMF stress-strain response of specimen G

Fig. 13 Comparison Isothermal and TMF results for specimens tests at 483 MPa (a) elastic modulus and (b) accumulated strain as a function of fatigue cycle, symbol table applies to both figures.

In this regime of testing, TMF does not degrade stiffness any differently than isothermal fatigue testing. There is also some indication that strain accumulation does not occur at lower loads in TMF testing. However, Fig. 13 (b) seems to indicate that TMF may accelerate strain ratcheting in higher loads. The manufacturing induced residual stresses are expected to be the principle mechanism that would accelerate damage and deformation in TMF testing of this polyimide composites. These stresses out of phase with the applied mechanical loads, i.e. they are low at elevated temperature and increase as the specimen cools down to 32 °C. In this way the material is continuously subjected to internal and external stresses. However, the absence of accumulated strain in TMF response of specimen E and the presence of accumulated strain at elevated stresses seem to indicate that time and external load at temperature are the significant factors. A telling creep experiment made Castelli et al [6] supports this speculation. By holding the load on the SMC composite constant and quasi-statically increasing temperature, it was shown that the onset of creep strain occurred at lower temperatures at higher static loads[6]. Clearly further testing and analysis is necessary to verify this trend and it will be important to determine if this trend carries over to unstitched materials.

Microscopic observations will play a role in these investigations. Using replication techniques described in [11] replicas are being made in tension and compression at low loads. Preliminary investigation shows that the dominant feature is the presence of significant porosity along the line of the out-of-plan stitch fibers. Residual stress tests will also be made on the remaining as fatigued specimens.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This effort is a part of the HOTPC collaboration between Boeing Rocketdyne and NASA-GRC developing a lightweight combustion support structure using polyimide composite. This ongoing study compares the isothermal and thermomechanical fatigue of stitched and unstitched cross-ply laminates of M40J carbon fiber reinforced HFPE-II-52 resin. Isothermal test temperature and the maximum cyclic temperature of TMF tests were chosen as the maximum operation temperature, 316 °C. The mechanical load cycle is identical in both isothermal and thermomechanical testing. Test waveforms for thermal and mechanical load cycles are in-phase and were chosen to be representative of an engine operation cycle. The load magnitudes were guided by the results of stress analysis of the actual component [1] and ranged from operating stresses of 138 MPa to 483 MPa or about 88% of the UTS. The progress reported here is for stitched materials only.

TMF testing of polymer composites is difficult due to the nature of the material and the desired TMF cycle; an overview of the testing methods applied here has been given above. An unexpected aberration in the thermal strain response was observed at maximum applied temperature and zero applied load. A variety of experiments were made that demonstrated that the measurement represented physical behavior. Pending further study the strain response for the TMF testing is reported as a total strain.

Thus far, four isothermal and three TMF tests have been completed. Elastic modulus was monitored throughout the test program but did not degrade with fatigue for either mode of testing. The main change in material performance was an accumulated strain that increased in proportion to test duration and applied load. The magnitude of accumulated strains ranged from 0.01% for 500 cycles at 138 MPa peak load to 0.4% for 500 cycles at 483 MPa peak load. The strain accumulation did not occur in the TMF test made at 276 MPa for 1623 cycles but 0.05% strain did accumulate after 2000 cycles of isothermal fatigue at the same load level. TMF does not seem to accelerate strain accumulation at lower load levels. Presently it is speculated that time and external load at temperature are the factors controlling this strain ratcheting effect. Further testing is planned to verify this observation and to determine the influence of stitching.

The data acquired does provide some initial design guidelines. Only one specimen failed in fatigue. This was at twice the expected operating load of the support structure and only after about eight times the required service life of 200 cycles. Specimens peak loaded to 88% of the UTS were found to survive about 2.5 times the required service life without failure. There appears to be a good margin of safety to the life requirement at operations load. Isothermal fatigue at the operation load level of 138 MPa caused 0.01% strain accumulation in 500 cycles which would be equivalent to an increase in structural compliance of 7% at that load level. Similarly 0.05% accumulative strain at 276 MPa peak load would cause an increase in structural compliance of about 15% after 2000 cycles. This information will aid the determination of stiffness requirements for lightweight designs so that deflections remain within the limits over the service life of the part.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

NASA-GRC Aeropropulsion Program Office: Higher Operating Temperature Propulsion Components (HOTPC) Project. J. Rodney Ellis(NASA-GRC) and Michael Castelli (OAI) for discussions regarding TMF test methods. Bradley Lerch and Cheryl Bowman (NASA-GRC) for

reviewing the paper and providing helpful comments. Joe Lavelle and Tim Ubienski at NASA-GRC for specimen preparation.

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